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Feminist Reading on Manju Kapur's *Home*

by **Shadman Akhtar**, *Department of English,
Andaman College (ANCOL), Port Blair - 744101, India*

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Abstract:

The last decade of the twentieth century witnessed a sudden spurt in feminist writing in Indian English fiction. A group of Indian women novelists in them in betweenness, hybridity of thought and multicultural, multi-lingual and multi-religious social dimensions have contextualized the particular. Manju Kapur is a contemporary Indian Novelist in English. Kapur's novel, Home is about Nisha who longs for a meaningful career, but is forced into waiting for marriage. Dedicated to Manju Kapur's children - Amba, Maya, Katyayani and Agastya - the novel Home (2006) moves forward through the conflicting polarities of tradition and modernity, poverty and prosperity, man and woman concerns.

Introduction:

The last decade of the twentieth century witnessed a sudden spurt in feminist writing in Indian English fiction. A group of Indian women novelists in them in betweenness, hybridity of thought and multicultural, multilingual and multi-religious social dimensions have contextualized the particular. While the gynocritics

think that too many women in too many countries speak the same language of silence, some Indian women novelists like Gita Hariharan, Shashi Deshpande, Arundhati Roy, Meena Alexander and Manju Kapur have tried with sincerity and honesty to deal with the physical, psychological and emotional stress syndrome of women.

The process of women being made a possession of man is a gradual one. Historical and sociological aspects seem to have contributed their share in keeping behind curtain. The slow but steady changes in cultural, social and economic patterns of life have expanded and altered the nature of reality for women. Women are born free, but she is in chains. She has become subordinate sex, but not always everywhere. All women do not conform to tradition, they rebel.

Discussion:

Manju Kapur is a contemporary Indian Novelist in English. Kapur's novel, *Home* is about Nisha who longs for a meaningful career, but is forced into waiting for marriage. Dedicated to Manju Kapur's children - Amba, Maya, Katyayani and Agastya - the novel *Home* (2006) moves forward through the conflicting polarities of tradition and modernity, poverty and prosperity, man and woman concerns. The novel presents the picture of a joint family - the Banwari Lala - which pursues business with all its heart. The family cannot think of employment opportunities for its sons and grandsons. The two sons of Banwari Lal - Yashpal and Pyare Lal - are well settled in business and are married, the former to Sona and the latter to Sushila. Banwari Lal's daughter, Sunita is wedded to Murali, a jobless man of irritable nature believing in dowry and responsible for the burning of Sunita at the age of 32, leaving behind her only son, Vicky, a lean and thin boy of shy nature, to the care of maternal uncles and their parents. Speaking of the Banwari Lal family, the novelist writes thus: "The Banwari Lal family belonged to a class whose skills had been honored over generations to ensure prosperity in the market-place. Their marriages augmented, their habits conserved"

And, in Chapter VI a pen-portrait of the two differing sisters is presented at some length: Two sisters more different than Sona and Rupa he could not imagine. One self-obsessed, complaining and dissatisfied, the other a well of sweet water from which everyone drank, (70).

Both the sisters are the victims of 'thwarted maternal instinct' but they take it in a diametrically opposed attitude. For long ten years, Sona practices penance and austerities and is, thereafter, blessed with Nisha (daughter) and Raju's son. As against this, Rupa never seems to bother about a child. Instead, her comet to the rescue of Sona and Yashpal when they were extremely worried about the nocturnal screams of Nisha and her increasingly dwindling health. Rupa carries away Nisha to her house and nourishes her back to normal health. Rupa's husband, a busy clerk in a Central Government office (Defence Ministry), arranges for Nisha's proper education, even tutors her in spare hours, and makes her a bright student. On the strength of his tutoring, Nisha is able to do her BA (more about Nisha later on).

Before we examine some of the problems relating to the world of woman-kind, it would be perhaps convenient to take into account the title of the novel - *Home*. The family tree, as drawn by the writer, clearly mentions the 'home' of the Banwari Lal's which is a large family of two sons, Yashpal and Pyarelal, and their wives, Sona and Sushila, and a daughter called Sunita. The only daughter of the Lal's is married off to a cruel and wine addicted man, who does not even try to improve the financial conditions of his home. He rather wishes that Sunita's parental family should invest in Bareilly; it should either open an outlet that he would manage, or failing that, to help upgrade his shop (p.18).

But Sunita resists him, as she does not allow him to exploit her father. Consequently, her home becomes a hell, and she dies of burns in the kitchen at the age of 32, leaving behind her small son, Vicky, to the care of God knows who.

Vicky is taken to Delhi by the Lal's to bring him up there, much to the irritation of Sona, whose responsibilities at home increased with his arrival. A lean and thin boy, Vicky is also weak in studies. He is almost a neglected child, and his conduct towards Nisha is dirty and creil: Deceitful, cunning, his father's son, not poor Sunita's (76). But Vicky does not agree to this proposal, and threatens to kill himself if he is forced to go back to Bareilly. In the latter part of the novel, the problems of Nisha, a college-going girl, are discussed in detail-her enrolment in DBC as a BA student, her sudden meeting with engineering boy called Suresh Kumar in a bus and their subsequent love-affairs, the boy's poverty and caste (a Paswan as he is) coming as a hurdle in the fulfilment of this love, the tormenting eczema of

Nisha, her teaching in a nursery school as a pass time, her setting up of Nisha's Creations (a shop for preparing bridal suits), and her eventual marriage with Arvind, a widower of 34 having a motor parts shop of his own.

Another concern of the female world is the curse of barrenness. The novel under consideration thrown up this issue abundantly. The curse of barrenness initially overtakes both Sona and Rupa (real sisters), but subsequently Sona is lessed with a daughter (Nisha) and a son (Raju). Sona becomes a mother after an anxious wait of ten long years, after passing many sleepless nights, after severe penance and prayers. She prays to Lord Krishna thus: "... please, I am growing old, bless us with a child, girl or boy, I do not care, but I cannot bear emptiness in my heart" (20). To fill the emptiness Sona and Yashpal adopt the orphaned Vicky as their son, but Sona is not happy with this decision. She says, "A borrowed child? Ten years old? From another woman's womb?"(23).

Her cruelty is verily inspired by her sense of security and purity. She has actually set her eyes on marriage with Suresh, and before that she cannot enjoy 'the forbidden pleasures'. She has made up her mind to marry Suresh: "Either I marry him or nobody" (201), but two things pose a great problem before her family- caste and poverty. Under pressures from the Banwari Lals, Suresh and his parents' wilt. Suresh is though hurt within, does not have the guts to declare his promise of marriage with Nisha before her people. Instead, he says, "I will do whatever is best for everyone.

Home is a mild representation of feminism where Nisha, stricken with a skin disease, marries a widower, Arvind. Streaks of independence are however noticeable in Nisha when she starts a business and leaves her job. Economic independent opens for her doors of happiness. Thus, all the three novels of Manju Kapur seem to break the preconceived notions and image of Indian woman as they do not conform to the stereotyped roles society has assigned to them. They have no fixed characteristics, accept challenges attain their individuality and successfully come out of their shells. The new Indian woman is emerging, embarking on a journey of freedom.

Conclusion:

The novels of Manju Kapur voice well the sentiments of women and their self-introspections. The women in the novels of Manju Kapur seem to be the personification of new women who have been carrying the burden of inhibition since ages and want to be free now. The writer clearly shows the dilemma of women who carry the burden of being female as well as the added responsibility of being mothers to members of their own sex. In the traditional social milieu of the novel where mothers and daughters exist, marriage is regarded as the ultimate goal and destiny from which these women cannot escape. Manju Kapur succeeds in presenting the real picture of women in a male-dominated society. Her female protagonists are mostly educated aspiring individuals caged within the confines of a conservative society.

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